
Farm machinery

Hydrotillers for wetland ricefields

G. R. Quick and H. T. Manaligod, Agricultural Engineering Division; and L. B. Aclan, Experimental Farm, IRRI

The IRRI Hydrotiller is a semifloating rototiller designed to puddle and level soil and to incorporate residues, weeds, or green manure in waterlogged or submerged ricefields. Two models—1.0 m working width (requiring 7-10 hp engine) and 0.8 m working width (requiring 5-6 hp)—are now in commercial production in Southeast Asia.

IRRI has used these Hydrotillers on its research farm field plots and seed increase areas. Advantages are as follows:

- High maneuverability, for speedy puddling and land preparation.
- Capable of working in areas inaccessible to wheeled tractors or water buffalo.
- The entire area of plot or farm field parcel is worked over because the machine cultivates to the edges of bunds, trims edges and corners, and controls and incorporates weeds.
- Two passes at right angles can prepare well-soaked fields or plots for transplanting or direct seeding, without plowing and harrowing.

New IRRI hydrotiller (1.0 m working width) being used to incorporate stubbles in a puddled ricefield.

The 0.8-m Hydrotiller is small enough to be carried by two people. It is maneuverable enough to work in very small plot areas, even as small as 10 m². The regular Hydrotiller can work up to 2 ha with two passes in an 8-h day. It can incorporate *Sesbania rostrata* up to 1.5 m tall (the 0.8-m Hydrotiller cannot work tall green crops or heavy weeds). The twin hulls of the hydrotillers leave no permanent trails, and normal transplant-

ing or direct seeding operations can follow shortly after working with the machines.

Costs in the Philippines are around US\$1300 for the 1.0-m Hydrotiller, including 10-hp gasoline engine, and \$700 for the 0.8-m Mini Hydrotiller, including 5-hp engine with half-speed power takeoff. Blueprints are available free to potential manufacturers from IRRI's Agricultural Engineering Division. ■

ENVIRONMENT

Meteorological aspects of wet season rice cultivation in Sunderbans region, India

M. K. Khandelwal, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute (CSSRI), Indian Council of Agricultural Research, Regional Research Station, Canning Town 743329, West Bengal, India

We used three dual-purpose volumetric type rectangular metallic lysimeters (1.2 × 1.2 × 0.90 m) sunk in the middle of well-exposed fields to record crop data.

Daily meteorological data of weeks 30-43 for 6 yr 1982-88 were collected from the CSSRI meteorological observatory at 88°40' E longitude, 22°15' N latitude, and 3 m altitude.

Local improved, salt-resistant, waterlogging-tolerant varieties CSR4 and CR6 were planted in the lysimeter at 15 × 15-cm spacing during the wet seasons. Abstracted mean weekly values of rainfall (R), pan evaporation (PE), lysimetric evapotranspiration [ET(L)], and calculated crop coefficient (Ckp) were recorded Jul-Oct (Table 1).

Weekly PE ranged from 25 mm (Oct) to 31 mm (Aug). ET(L) ranged from 29 mm (Jul) to 39 mm (Oct). Based on ET/PE, Ckp ranged from 1.08 (Jul) to 1.57 (Oct), with an average of 1.30 for the season.

Observed ET(L) was compared with computed potential evapotranspiration (PET) (unadjusted/grass reference/alfalfa reference) by nine empirical methods: Blaney-Criddle (2), Christiansen Default Option, Hargreaves, Jensen-Haise, Turc, Modified Penman, Radiation, and Thornthwaite (Table 1). Coefficient of